

Capacitor Degradation Monitoring for LLC Resonant Converter based on Discharging Profile

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Abstract—The Multi-layer Ceramic (MLC) capacitor is a critical yet vulnerable component in power electronic converters, where degradation leads to a decrease in capacitance. Monitoring capacitance is crucial for predicting the lifespan of MLC capacitors, ensuring the safe and reliable operation of converters. This paper introduces a monitoring scheme specifically for LLC resonant converters that estimates the capacitance of its capacitor on the output side. The scheme leverages large-signal discharging transient trajectories for estimating MLC capacitor parameters without the need for extra sensors. By examining the relationship between these trajectories and the capacitor parameters, capacitance is determined using a calculation model based on the output voltage and current transient trajectory. Corresponding simulation and experimental analysis is conducted in the end.

Index Terms—Condition monitoring, LLC converter, Multi-layer ceramic capacitor

I. INTRODUCTION

DC-link capacitors play a pivotal role in the functionality of most electronic converters, offering essential benefits such as suppression of DC-link voltage ripple, absorption of harmonics, and balancing the instantaneous power difference between the front and rear ends of converter systems. Additionally, in certain applications, they provide critical energy support during transient and abnormal operations. Despite their importance, capacitors are susceptible to thermal and electrical stresses, which significantly limit their lifespan and increase their degradation failure rate [1]. Research reveals that about 30% of converter faults are attributable to capacitor degradation, highlighting them as a notable vulnerability within power electronic systems [2]. Consequently, it is crucial to monitor the degradation state of capacitors and implement proactive maintenance. Such measures are not only essential for ensuring the reliable operation of DC-link applications but are also critical in averting potential catastrophic failures, underscoring the necessity of capacitor health management.

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TABLE I: Degradation indicators.

Indicators		Indicator acquisition methods
Electrical	R_{ESR} , C , Z_c , etc.	LCR meter, etc. Parameters estimation
Non-electrical	Struture	X-ray image meter
		Optical inspection meter
		Thermography meter
		Acoustic detection meter
Temperature	Temperature	Thermography meter
		Internal temperature
		Weight
Pressure	Pressure	Weighing meter
		Internal pressure sensor

In recent years, a significant surge in condition monitoring (CM) techniques for DC-link capacitors has been observed [3]. Essentially, as capacitors degrade, they undergo a range of physical and chemical transformations internally, which may lead to alterations in both non-electrical parameters, including weight, structural integrity, internal temperature, and internal pressure and electrical parameters, such as Equivalent Series Resistance (ESR), Capacitance (C), impedance, dissipation factor, and parallel resistance [4]. Table I lists the common indicators and their acquisition methods. Monitoring these indicators allows for an assessment of a capacitor health and operational state, facilitating timely maintenance actions to prevent failure and ensure system reliability. For example, the acoustic detection is proposed in [5] to monitor the damage of MLC capacitors using support vector machine classifier. Furthermore, in [6], a lock-in thermography is utilized to detect failures for capacitors based on the thermal response. However, condition monitoring schemes that rely on non-electrical parameters typically necessitate the use of high-cost measurement instruments. Moreover, the lack of clear, universally applicable end-of-life indicators undermines the effectiveness of non-electrical parameter-based CM schemes, making them less favorable compared to their electrical parameter-based counterparts in various applications.

Despite the availability of non-electrical indicators for monitoring capacitor health, research predominantly focuses on electrical indicators, as they can provide quantifiable and

immediate insights into the capacitor conditions. Among the various electrical indicators used for monitoring the health of capacitors, equivalent series resistance and capacitance are particularly favored and selected as end-of-life criteria [7]–[9]. The estimations of these indicators can be achieved through either online or offline methods [3]. Online methods, in particular, offer the advantage of monitoring capacitor health without interrupting the converter normal operations, usually relying on understanding the relationship between ripple voltage or current within a specific converter model. For example, a current sensor less condition monitoring method in proposed in [10] for a DC link capacitor in a three phase PWM inverter with a front-end six-pulse diode rectifier and a DC inductor. A recursive least square estimator is utilized in [11] to detect changes for the capacitance in modular multilevel converters. Conversely, offline methods necessitate pausing system operations to physically disconnect the capacitor for measurement. For example, a new submodule capacitor condition monitoring method is presented in [12] based on the DC-side start-up procedure. An LC resonance is introduced in [13] intentionally to generate a safe but large amplitude currents that are theoretically related to the capacitor capacitance.

Although a substantial research exists on the estimation of equivalent series resistance for capacitors and capacitance, it predominantly focuses on specific types of converters, such as buck converters, boost converters, and others. This concentration suggests a potential gap in the literature regarding the application of estimation techniques to other types of converters or in different contexts, such as LLC resonant converter. Considering the challenges in establishing a direct relationship between ripple voltage and current in LLC converters, a large-signal discharging transient dynamics-based method has been designed for estimating the capacitance of multi-layer ceramic capacitors.

II. THEORY OF OPERATION

In power electronic systems, DC-link capacitors are pivotal for maintaining voltage stability and energy storage, necessitating a carefully considered design. Typically, a capacitor bank is strategically placed at the DC link in a series-parallel configuration to mitigate ripple current effects. The selection of capacitors is critical, with Aluminum Electrolytic Capacitors (Al-Caps), Metallized Polypropylene Film Capacitors (MPPF-Caps), and Multi-layer ceramic capacitors being the primary choices.

A. Aging Indicators

DC-link capacitors are susceptible to failures arising from a myriad of intrinsic and extrinsic factors, encompassing design defects, material wear out, operating conditions like temperature, voltage and current, as well as environmental influences such as moisture and mechanical stress. These failures typically manifest in two primary forms: catastrophic failure, which occurs suddenly due to single-event overstress (such as a surge in voltage or current beyond the capacitor tolerance), and wear-out failure, which results from the gradual

Fig. 1: Simplified lumped capacitor model.

TABLE II: Typical end-of-life criteria of capacitors.

	Al-Caps	MPPF-Caps	MLC-Caps
End-of-life criteria	$C/C_0 < 80\%$ $R_{ESR}/R_{ESR0} > 2$	$C/C_0 < 95\%$	$C/C_0 < 90\%$

degradation of the capacitor materials and performance over time. Catastrophic failures are often abrupt and unpredictable, leading to immediate loss of functionality, while wear-out failures develop slowly, reducing the capacitor effectiveness and efficiency until it no longer meets the required performance standards.

Fig. 1 shows a simplified model of capacitors characterized by key parameters, i.e. capacitance (C), equivalent series resistance (R_{ESR}), equivalent series inductance, insulation resistance (R_P), dielectric loss (R_D) and inherent dielectric absorption (C_D). The degradation of capacitors over time leads to changes in key parameters, which form the basis for establishing end-of-life (EOL) criteria. The typical end-of-life criteria for Al-Caps, MPPF-Caps, and MLC capacitors are listed in Table II, where it is often defined by a significant increase or decrease in equivalent series resistance and capacitance from its initial value (C_0 , R_{ESR0}) [14].

B. LLC Resonant Converter

The LLC resonant converter stands out as one of the most prevalent isolated DC/DC converters, acclaimed for its versatility and efficiency across a broad spectrum of applications. Its popularity can be attributed to several key advantages, including high efficiency, the ability to handle wide input voltage ranges, and its inherent zero-voltage switching (ZVS) capability, which reduces switching losses and improves overall performance. As a result, LLC resonant converters are increasingly favored in applications where efficiency and power density are critical, such as in renewable energy systems and electric vehicle charging solutions [15]. The LLC topology, combining inductance and capacitance in a resonant circuit with a full-bridge rectifier configuration is shown in Fig. 2.

The converter configuration has three main parts:

1) Power switches $S_1 - S_4$, typically MOSFETs, are arranged to form a square-wave generator. This configuration is instrumental in producing a unipolar square-wave voltage, by alternately activating each switch with around 50% duty cycles. A carefully calibrated dead time is introduced between

Fig. 2: Topology of the full-bridge LLC resonant converter with an equivalent capacitor model.

the transitions of S_1 and S_2 , allowing the prevention of cross-conduction and achieving the ZVS.

2) The resonant circuit, or resonant network, is designed to facilitate efficient energy transfer and conversion, which comprises the resonant capacitance (C_r) and two inductances: the series resonant inductance (L_r) and the transformer magnetizing inductance (L_m). The process begins with the transformer primary winding receiving a bipolar square-wave voltage, which is then effectively transmitted to the secondary side of the transformer. Here, the transformer not only provides electrical isolation, but also adjusts the voltage to the required level at the output through its turns ratio.

3) In the secondary side of converter, diodes arranged in a full-bridge rectifier configuration efficiently convert AC input to DC output, catering to the load (R_L). An output capacitor is integral to this topology, ensuring the rectified voltage and current are smoothed, thus providing a stable DC supply. For enhanced efficiency, especially in low-voltage, high-current scenarios, a shift towards synchronous rectification using MOSFETs instead of diodes can reduce conduction losses.

For LLC resonant converter, the series resonant frequency f_r , parallel resonant frequency f_m , normalized switching frequency f_n , quality factor Q , and inductor ratio K are defined as:

$$f_r = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{L_r C_r}} \quad (1)$$

$$f_m = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{(L_r + L_m)C_r}} \quad (2)$$

$$f_n = \frac{f_s}{f_r} \quad (3)$$

$$f_r = \frac{\sqrt{L_r/C_r}}{Z_{ac}} \quad (4)$$

$$K = \frac{L_m}{L_r} \quad (5)$$

where f_s is the switching frequency; Z_{ac} is the equivalent impedance of the secondary rectifier

In the secondary side of an LLC converter under research, multi-layer ceramic capacitors are utilized in this paper for their low equivalent series resistance and high frequency response.

III. PROPOSED MONITORING SCHEME

MLC capacitors can experience accelerated degradation, primarily due to the ‘amplifying’ effect associated with their numerous dielectric layers. While the layered structure of MLC capacitors contributes to their high capacitance values within compact sizes, it also makes them more susceptible to wear and tear that can lead to premature failure. Insulation degradation and flex cracking will also cause the failure in MLC capacitors. Insulation degradation occurs as the dielectric layer thickness decreases over time, either through normal wear or excessive voltage stress, leading to increased leakage currents. Flex cracking, on the other hand, is a mechanical failure resulting from physical stress, such as board flexure or thermal expansion, which can create cracks in the ceramic material.

The failure of MLC capacitors in power converters is particularly concerning because they often fail in a short circuit mode, which can have drastic consequences for the entire power system, potentially leading to significant damage or operational disruption. To effectively monitor the degradation of multi-layer ceramic capacitors, the discharging profile-based capacitance estimation method is proposed by observing the capacitor voltage over time without the need for extra sensors.

A. Calculation Model of Capacitance

The monitoring technique leverages the relationship between capacitance, voltage, and time as defined by the capacitor discharge equation. A deviation from the expected discharge profile suggests alterations in the capacitor physical condition, such as a reduction in dielectric layer thickness or the presence of micro-cracks, both of which affect the ability to store and release energy.

During the discharging period, the capacitor voltage is expressed as:

$$V_{cap} = V_{dc} e^{-\frac{t}{(R_{ESR}+R_L)C}} \quad (6)$$

where V_{cap} and V_{dc} are the capacitor and bus voltages, respectively. Fig. 3 shows the transient response waveform during power down process.

Fig. 3: Discharging profile during converter power down process.

Fig. 4: Flowchart representation of the proposed condition monitoring algorithm.

(a) $R_{ESR} = 50m\Omega$, $R_L = 4\Omega$.

(b) $R_{ESR} = 150m\Omega$, $R_L = 4\Omega$.

Fig. 5: Simulation results for the case under different ESR conditions.

B. Estimation Algorithm

The capacitor condition monitoring procedure is applied for converter operating during power down process. Fig. 4 illustrates the different parts of the procedures by a flowchart. Usually, the converter operates under normal conditions. As the system approaches the scheduled shutdown, the process for estimation is initiated.

The process begins by sending a zero vector to the MOSFETs, effectively turning them off. Simultaneously, the system processor begins to capture the converter output voltage and current measurements, facilitated by voltage and current sensors, until the converter has fully powered down. Finally, the estimation is derived from analyzing the observed capacitor

(a) $C = 220\mu F$, $R_{ESR} = 100m\Omega$.

(b) $C = 100\mu F$, $R_{ESR} = 100m\Omega$.

Fig. 6: Simulation results for the case under different C conditions.

discharging profile, based on (6).

Remark 1: Considering that the ESR is relatively smaller than the load, it is therefore assumed that R_{ESR} can be neglected in (6).

Remark 2: The procedure for capacitance estimation varies based on whether the load resistance is known or unknown. If the resistance of the load R_L is known, the process for estimating the capacitance of the capacitor becomes more straightforward. Given that the time constant τ of a capacitor discharge through a resistor is $\tau = R_L \times C$, and knowing R_L , one can rearrange the discharge equation to solve for C directly after measuring the discharge time or analyzing the voltage decay profile over time, as shown in Fig. 3. If the load resistance is unknown, a two-step process is required. The first step involves estimating the load resistance itself, which can be achieved by measuring the voltage across the load and the current flowing through it. Once the load is determined, the subsequent estimation of the capacitor capacitance can then be achieved.

Remark 3: Based on Fig. 3, four sets of capacitance values (C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4) can be estimated from four fixed time points ($t = \tau, t = 2\tau, t = 3\tau$ and $t = 4\tau$), and the final estimation can be derived by calculation of their average values $C = (C_1 + C_2 + C_3 + C_4)/4$.

TABLE III: Estimation results under different capacitance and ESR values.

Loads (Ω)	Capacitors (μF)	ESRs ($m\Omega$)	Estimated C	
			Value (μF)	Error (%)
4	330	50	334.3	1.31
	330	100	330.4	1.17
	330	150	340.3	3.14
4	220	50	222.3	1.05
	220	100	220.6	1.20
	220	150	229.1	4.12
4	100	50	101.0	1.04
	100	100	100.5	1.36
	100	150	100.6	1.40

TABLE IV: Estimation results under different capacitance and load values.

ESR ($m\Omega$)	Capacitors (μF)	Loads (Ω)	Estimated C	
			Value (μF)	Error (%)
100	220	4	220.6	1.20
	220	8	221.4	0.63
	220	16	220.6	0.39
100	100	4	100.5	1.36
	100	8	100.7	0.77
	100	16	100.4	0.51

Remark 4: The proposed monitoring method for assessing capacitor health in converter utilizes existing voltage and current measurement points integrated into the converter control system. Therefore, no additional sensors are required to implement the monitoring method.

IV. SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To verify the proposed estimation method, LLC converter with different capacitor and load parameters are built in Simulink simulation environment. The main circuit parameters are given as follows: $V_{in} = 400V$, $V_o = 48V$, $L_r = 77\mu H$, $L_m = 429\mu H$, $C_r = 32pF$. It is noted that the C and R_{ESR} utilized in the simulation are assumed values.

In the secondary side of LLC converter, capacitors are connected in series with load and ESR, as shown in Fig. 2. Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 shows the output voltage and current dynamics with three different C ($330\mu F$, $220\mu F$, $100\mu F$) R_{ESR} ($50m\Omega$, $100m\Omega$, $150m\Omega$) and R_L (4Ω , 8Ω , 16Ω) values. It can be observed that the transient voltage and current trajectory changes when the capacitor parameters are changed. According to the transient trajectory and (6), the C can be estimated and listed in Table III and Table IV. It can be shown from Table III that the estimation error increases when the ESR is relatively large. However, the estimation error can be reduced by the increasing of load, as shown in Table IV. Therefore, the feasibility of the proposed method can be observed from the simulation results.

To test the proposed estimation method, experimental results are given in this section, where the output of LLC converter

(a) $C = 220\mu F$, $R_L = 110\Omega$.

(b) $C = 220\mu F$, $R_L = 220\Omega$.

Fig. 7: Experimental results for the case under different capacitance and resistance values.

(a) $C = 470\mu F$, $R_L = 110\Omega$.

(b) $C = 470\mu F$, $R_L = 220\Omega$.

Fig. 8: Experimental results for the case under different capacitance and resistance values.

is set as $V_o = 24V$. Figs. 7 to 9 give the capacitor discharge profiles at various capacitance, and resistance values.

V. CONCLUSION AND REMARKS

In this paper, a transient trajectory-based condition monitoring method is proposed to estimate the C of MLC capacitor for LLC resonant converters. Using the relationship between capacitor parameters and converter output voltage and current trajectory, the C is calculated. The main advantages of proposed condition monitoring method are as follows: 1) The implementation of proposed method relies only on the sensors required for converter control and avoids the installation of new sensors; 2) The method involves the analysis of large-signal transient trajectories without the need to measure high-frequency small ripple signals. The feasibility and effective-

(a) $C = 680\mu F$, $R_L = 110\Omega$.

(b) $C = 680\mu F$, $R_L = 220\Omega$.

Fig. 9: Experimental results for the case under different capacitance and resistance values.

ness of proposed methods are validated by simulation and experimental results.

However, the presented condition monitoring method is idealized as it depends on the strict assumption of a resistive load, which may not be practical. To address this challenge, an alternative and dedicated discharging path with a known-value resistor should be designed, and the load should be disconnected before measuring the capacitance.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Tan, B. Wei, J. C. Vasquez, and J. M. Guerrero, "Junction temperature estimation technologies of igbt modules in converter-based applications," in *IECON 2023-49th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [2] S. Yang, D. Xiang, A. Bryant, P. Mawby, L. Ran, and P. Tavner, "Condition monitoring for device reliability in power electronic converters: A review," *IEEE transactions on power electronics*, vol. 25, no. 11, pp. 2734–2752, 2010.
- [3] P. Sundararajan, M. H. M. Sathik, F. Sasongko, C. S. Tan, M. Tariq, and R. Simanjorang, "Online condition monitoring system for dc-link capacitor in industrial power converters," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 54, no. 5, pp. 4775–4785, 2018.
- [4] Z. Zhao, P. Davari, W. Lu, H. Wang, and F. Blaabjerg, "An overview of condition monitoring techniques for capacitors in dc-link applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 3692–3716, 2020.
- [5] S. Levikari, T. J. Kärkkäinen, C. Andersson, J. Tammiminen, and P. Silventoinen, "Acoustic detection of cracks and delamination in multilayer ceramic capacitors," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 55, no. 2, pp. 1787–1794, 2018.
- [6] C. Andersson, O. Kristensen, S. Miller, T. Gloor, and F. Iannuzzo, "Lock-in thermography failure detection on multilayer ceramic capacitors after flex cracking and temperature–humidity–bias stress," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 2254–2261, 2018.
- [7] P. Sundararajan, M. H. M. Sathik, F. Sasongko, C. S. Tan, J. Pou, F. Blaabjerg, and A. K. Gupta, "Condition monitoring of dc-link capacitors using goertzel algorithm for failure precursor parameter and temperature estimation," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 6386–6396, 2019.
- [8] W. Miao, X. Liu, K. Lam, and P. W. Pong, "Condition monitoring of electrolytic capacitors in boost converters by magnetic sensors," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 19, no. 22, pp. 10 393–10 402, 2019.
- [9] F. Deng, Q. Heng, C. Liu, X. Cai, R. Zhu, Z. Chen, and W. Chen, "Capacitor esr and c monitoring in modular multilevel converters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 4063–4075, 2019.
- [10] K. Hasegawa, T. Kubo, and Y. Hirose, "Current-sensor-less condition monitoring of a dc-link capacitor in a pwm inverter with a six-pulse diode rectifier," *IEEE Journal of Industry Applications*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 548–554, 2023.
- [11] M. Asoodar, M. Nahalparvari, C. Danielsson, R. Söderström, and H.-P. Nee, "Online health monitoring of dc-link capacitors in modular multilevel converters for facts and hvdc applications," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 12, pp. 13 489–13 503, 2021.
- [12] Z. Wang, Y. Zhang, H. Wang, and F. Blaabjerg, "Capacitor condition monitoring based on the dc-side start-up of modular multilevel converters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 5589–5593, 2019.
- [13] H. Li, D. Xiang, X. Han, X. Zhong, and X. Yang, "High-accuracy capacitance monitoring of dc-link capacitor in vsi systems by lc resonance," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 34, no. 12, pp. 12 200–12 211, 2019.
- [14] H. Wang and F. Blaabjerg, "Reliability of capacitors for dc-link applications in power electronic converters—an overview," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 50, no. 5, pp. 3569–3578, 2014.
- [15] Y. Wei, Q. Luo, and A. Mantooh, "Overview of modulation strategies for llc resonant converter," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 10, pp. 10 423–10 443, 2020.